

[microresearch]

Diamond Open Access

[awaiting peer review]

Modeling of a Viscoelastic System with Fractional Derivative

Open Mathematics Collaboration*

November 22, 2024

Abstract

We present an application of fractional differential equations in the modeling of viscoelastic systems. We consider a viscoelastic system represented by the fractional Kelvin-Voigt model and use the analytical method of the Laplace transform to solve the fractional differential equation associated with the system. Finally, we present a numerical simulation of the analytical solution obtained.

keywords: fractional differential equations, viscoelastic systems, Laplace transform

The most updated version of this white paper is available at
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14204902>

Introduction

1. This article primarily relies on references [1–3].
2. Fractional differential equations represent a generalization of traditional differential equations, allowing derivatives of non-integer order, known as fractional-order derivatives.
3. Mathematical models for viscoelastic materials, such as the Maxwell and Kelvin-Voigt models, use integer-order differential equations to describe the relationship between stress and strain.

*All *authors* and their *affiliations* are listed at the end of this white paper.

4. In this article, we use fractional differential equations to model a viscoelastic system represented by the fractional Kelvin-Voigt model. The inclusion of fractional-order derivatives provides a more accurate representation of the system's memory properties.
5. We use the Laplace transform to find an analytical solution for the fractional differential equation that defines the fractional Kelvin-Voigt model. Subsequently, we present a numerical simulation of the analytical solution through an example.

Fractional Calculus

6. We establish some important concepts and properties of fractional calculus, based on the Caputo fractional derivative.
7. Let $f : [0, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function of class C^n . The Caputo fractional derivative of f of order $\alpha \geq 0$ is defined by

$${}^C D^\alpha f(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{n-\alpha-1} f^n(\tau) d\tau, & \text{if } \alpha \notin \mathbb{N}, n = [\alpha] + 1, \\ f(t), & \text{if } \alpha = 0, \end{cases}$$

where $[\alpha]$ denotes the integer part of α (see [1]).

8. The Γ function is defined by

$$\Gamma(z) = \int_0^{+\infty} \tau^{z-1} e^{-\tau} d\tau,$$

for $z \in \mathbb{C}$ with $\text{Re}(z) > 0$ (the real part of z is positive).

9. Note that ${}^C D^\alpha f(t) = f^n(t)$ if $\alpha = n \in \mathbb{N}$.
10. Let $\alpha \geq 0$ and $n = [\alpha] + 1$. Then, the Laplace transform of the Caputo fractional derivative of f of order α is given by

$$\mathcal{L}\left({}^C D^\alpha f(t)\right)(s) = s^\alpha \mathcal{L}\left(f(t)\right)(s) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} f^k(0) s^{\alpha-k-1},$$

where $f^k(0)$ are the initial conditions (see [1, Lemma 2.24]).

11. The two-parameter Mittag-Leffler function $E_{\alpha, \beta}$, for some $\alpha, \beta > 0$ and $z \in \mathbb{C}$, is defined by

$$E_{\alpha, \beta}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + \beta)}$$

(see [1]).

12. Let $E_{\alpha, \beta}$ be the two-parameter Mittag-Leffler function for some $\alpha, \beta > 0$. Also let $a \in \mathbb{R}$. Then, for $s > |a|$,

$$\mathcal{L}\left(t^{\beta-1} \cdot E_{\alpha, \beta}(\pm at^{\alpha})\right)(s) = \frac{s^{\alpha-\beta}}{s^{\alpha} \mp a}$$

(see [2, Lemma 8.12]).

13. When $\beta = 1$ and $z \in \mathbb{C}$, $E_{\alpha, \beta}(z)$ coincides with the Mittag-Leffler function $E_{\alpha}(z)$,

$$E_{\alpha, 1}(z) = E_{\alpha}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(1 + \alpha k)}.$$

Viscoelastic System with Fractional Derivative

14. We consider a viscoelastic system represented by the fractional Kelvin-Voigt model (see [3]).
15. In the fractional Kelvin-Voigt model, the relationship between the stress $\sigma(t)$, or applied external force, and the strain $\epsilon(t)$ is determined by:

$$\sigma(t) = m\epsilon(t) + \eta^C D^{\alpha}\epsilon(t),$$

where:

- m : is the modulus of elasticity;
- η : is the material characteristic parameter;
- α : is the fractional order of the Caputo derivative;
- ${}^C D^{\alpha}$: is the Caputo fractional derivative of order α .

16. We consider that the external force $\sigma(t)$ is a unit step function (Heaviside function):

$$\sigma(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } t \geq 0, \\ 0, & \text{if } t < 0. \end{cases}$$

17. Substituting this function into the fractional differential equation given in (15), we obtain

$$1 = m\epsilon(t) + \eta^C D^\alpha \epsilon(t).$$

18. Rearranging terms, we obtain the equation

$$\eta^C D^\alpha \epsilon(t) + m\epsilon(t) = 1.$$

Application of the Laplace Transform

19. The Laplace transform of a function $g : [0, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}(g(t))(s) = \int_0^{+\infty} g(t)e^{-st} dt,$$

for $s \in \mathbb{C}$ at values where this integral exists (see [2]).

20. Applying the Laplace transform to the fractional differential equation found in (18), we obtain

$$\mathcal{L}(\eta^C D^\alpha \epsilon(t) + m\epsilon(t))(s) = \mathcal{L}(1)(s),$$

where s is the Laplace variable.

21. Using the linearity of the Laplace transform and (19), we have

$$\eta \mathcal{L}({}^C D^\alpha \epsilon(t)) + m\mathcal{L}(\epsilon(t))(s) = \frac{1}{s}.$$

22. Now, we use the Laplace transform of the Caputo fractional derivative of ϵ of order $\alpha \geq 0$, defined in (10). Assuming that the initial conditions are zero, that is, $\epsilon(0) = 0$ and $\epsilon^k(0) = 0$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$, we obtain

$$\mathcal{L}({}^C D^\alpha \epsilon(t)) = s^\alpha \mathcal{L}(\epsilon(t))(s).$$

23. Substituting this into (21), we get

$$\eta s^\alpha \mathcal{L}(\epsilon(t))(s) + m\mathcal{L}(\epsilon(t))(s) = \frac{1}{s}.$$

24. Thus,

$$\mathcal{L}(\epsilon(t))(s) = \frac{1}{s(\eta s^\alpha + m)}.$$

Inverse Laplace Transform

25. To find the solution for the strain $\epsilon(t)$, we need the inverse Laplace transform of (24).

26. The equation in (24) can be rewritten as

$$\mathcal{L}(\epsilon(t))(s) = \frac{1}{ms(\mu s^\alpha + 1)},$$

where $\mu = \frac{\eta}{m}$.

27. To invert the Laplace transform in (24), we need to use the Mittag-Leffler function, defined in (13), which is an extension of the classical exponential function.

28. Considering the properties of the Mittag-Leffler function, as defined in (13), and its Laplace transform (12),

$$\mathcal{L}(E_\alpha(-at^\alpha))(s) = \frac{s^{\alpha-1}}{s^\alpha + a}.$$

29. Observe that

$$\frac{1}{s(\mu s^\alpha + 1)} = \frac{1}{s} - \frac{s^{\alpha-1}}{s^\alpha + \frac{1}{\mu}}.$$

30. Using (21), (28) and (29), we have

$$\frac{1}{s(\mu s^\alpha + 1)} = \mathcal{L}\left(1 - E_\alpha\left(-\frac{t^\alpha}{\mu}\right)\right)(s).$$

31. Thus, the inverse Laplace transform is

$$\mathcal{L}^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{s(\mu s^\alpha + 1)}\right) = 1 - E_\alpha\left(-\frac{t^\alpha}{\mu}\right).$$

32. Therefore, applying the inverse Laplace transform into (26), we obtain the solution for the strain:

$$\epsilon(t) = \frac{1}{m}\left(1 - E_\alpha\left(-\frac{t^\alpha}{\mu}\right)\right),$$

where $\mu = \frac{\eta}{m}$.

Numerical Simulation

33. To illustrate the applicability of the analytical solution for the strain $\epsilon(t)$ obtained in (32), we consider the following parameters:

- Modulus of elasticity: $m = 1000$ Pa;
- Material characteristic parameter: $\eta = 500$ Pa;
- Fractional order α : we consider different values $\alpha_1 = 0.7$; $\alpha_2 = 0.8$; $\alpha_3 = 0.9$ and $\alpha_4 = 1$.

34. Substituting the parameter values m and η into (32), we have:

$$\epsilon(t) = \frac{1}{1000} (1 - E_\alpha(-2t^\alpha)).$$

35. We used MATLAB software to plot the strain function ϵ over time t .

36. The numerical implementation involves calculating the Mittag-Leffler function, which is defined by the series in (13), for various values of t .

37. For different fractional orders α , the Mittag-Leffler function $E_\alpha(-2t^\alpha)$ can be numerically approximated by a truncated series.

38. In the MATLAB implementation, the Mittag-Leffler function $E_\alpha(-2t^\alpha)$ is approximated using a truncated series with up to 100 terms. For greater precision, the number of terms can be increased.

39. Figure 1 represents the temporal evolution of strain $\epsilon(t)$ in the viscoelastic material, highlighting the influence of the fractional order on the system's response.

40. For each fractional order α_i , $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$, defined in (33), the graph shows a smooth transition between the instantaneous elastic response and the energy dissipation.

41. When $\alpha = 1$, the classical behavior of the Kelvin-Voigt model with integer-order derivatives is recovered.

Figure 1: Graph of strain $\epsilon(t)$ as a function of time t for the fractional viscoelastic model (18), with different fractional orders α_i , $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$, and parameters defined in (33).

Final Remarks

42. This article demonstrates the application of fractional differential equations in modeling viscoelastic systems, focusing on the fractional Kelvin-Voigt model. A key aspect of this work is the use of the Laplace transform to obtain an analytical solution for the fractional differential equation.
43. The use of the Mittag-Leffler function is critical in solving the fractional differential equation, as it extends the classical exponential function, providing a more accurate and flexible representation of the system's dynamics.
44. Numerical simulations effectively illustrate the analytical solution, highlighting the impact of fractional order on the viscoelastic behavior.
45. Fractional derivatives are powerful tools for modeling complex phenomena in science and engineering, encouraging further research.

Open Invitation

*Review, add content to, and co-author this white paper [4, 5].
Join the Open Mathematics Collaboration.*

Supplementary Files

[6]

How to Cite this White Paper

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14204902>

Acknowledgements

+ Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Agreement

All authors are in agreement with the guidelines presented in [5].

License

CC-By Attribution 4.0 International [7]

References

- [1] Kilbas, Anatoliĭ Aleksandrovich, Hari M. Srivastava, and Juan J. Trujillo. *Theory and applications of fractional differential equations*. Vol. 204. elsevier, 2006.
- [2] Diethelm, Kai, and N. J. Ford. “The analysis of fractional differential equations.” *Lecture notes in mathematics* 2004 (2010).

- [3] Mainardi, Francesco. *Fractional calculus and waves in linear viscoelasticity: an introduction to mathematical models*. World Scientific, 2022.
- [4] Lobo, Matheus P. “Microarticles.” *OSF Preprints*, 28 Oct. 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ejrct>
- [5] Lobo, Matheus P. “Simple Guidelines for Authors: Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics.” *OSF Preprints*, 15 Nov. 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/fk836>
- [6] <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14204902>
- [7] CC. Creative Commons. *CC-By Attribution 4.0 International*.
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>

The Open Mathematics Collaboration

Alvaro Julio Yucra Hanco¹ (alvaro.hanco@ufnt.edu.br)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6280-8775>

¹Federal University of Northern Tocantins (Brazil)